

Impact of climate change: Whispering from the Sundarbans mangrove of Bangladesh

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Abstract

Bangladesh faces both predictable and unpredictable climate change impacts. The Sundarbans Delta is struggling with multiple climatic stressors notably sea level rise, tropical cyclones, storm surges, and salinization. Therefore, the study aims to assess the types of climatic stressors and their impacts on the flora and fauna of the Sundarbans mangrove of Bangladesh. Empirical data were collected from focus group discussions and key informant interviews. It was revealed that dune vegetation, mammals and reptiles are vulnerable to sea level rise. The recent tropical cyclones impacted Sundarbans through three primary mechanisms: wind damage, storm surge, and sedimentation. Many affected areas have become unsuitable for habitation. Strong wind destroys honey bee colonies causing high mortality. Woodpeckers, sea turtles and parrots are vulnerable to cyclones. Storm surges reduce the viability of seeds, seedling germination and seedling recruitment. The recovery of forest dynamics from cyclone damage can be altered by other kinds of changes to the landscape. The cyclones facilitated biological invasion in the highly affected areas. Sundari, the pioneer tree species suffers from various diseases with the increase of salinity. Salinity increases the tree mortality rate by reducing the production of new leaves, leaf longevity and the leaf area. The study advocated for integrated coastal and marine management. Monitoring the impact of climate change on the Royal Bengal Tiger, crocodiles and Sundari tree is highly warranted.

Keywords: Climate change, Sundarbans mangrove, UNESCO World Heritage Site, Ramsar Site, sea level rise, tropical cyclone, salinity

Introduction

Due to the increased rate of emissions of greenhouse gases from different an average global temperature increase of 0.6° to 0.9°C from 1900 to the present, occurred predominantly in the past 50 years (Waters *et al.* 2016; Hansen *et al.* 1981; Anderson *et al.* 2016; Beckage *et al.* 2008; Al-Ghussain 2019; Yoro & Daramola 2020). Sea-level rise as a consequence of global warming is caused by the increase in seawater temperatures resulting in the thermal expansion of water and melting of glacier and polar ice (Cazenave & Nerem 2004; Church *et al.* 2001; Nicholls & Cazenave 2010).

Bangladesh faces both predictable and unpredictable climate change impacts (Alam *et al.* 2020; Ali *et al.* 2019; Billah 2018; Chiba *et al.* 2017; Chakraborty 2023; Chowdhury *et al.* 2020; Dastagir 2015; Haque *et al.* 2020; Hasnat *et al.* 2020; Khan 2019, Mukhopadhyay *et al.* 2022; Rahman 2020; Rahman 2021; Rahman *et al.* 2021; Rahman 2022). The Sundarbans Delta is struggling with multiple climatic stressors notably sea level rise, tropical cyclones, storm surges, and salinization (Chakrabarty 2023; Chakraborty *et al.* 2023; Samanta *et al.* 2021; Tuladhar 2023; Visions 2023, Rahman 2023 a, b). Most of the rivers of Bangladesh flow from north to south, silting up the mangroves delta and draining into the Bay of Bengal (Bandyopadhyay *et al.* 2023; Hossain *et al.* 2023; van Maren *et al.* 2023). The mangrove is a transitional area between the freshwater rivers originating from the Ganges and the Bay of Bengal (Das 2023; Hossain *et al.* 2023; Jayanthi *et al.* 2023; Subramanian *et al.* 2023). The ecosystems as well as the luxuriant biodiversity of Sundarbans have strong interactions with marine environments (Sarkar & Bhattacharya 2003; Rahman 23 c, d, e, f). This UNESCO World Heritage Site and Ramsar Site is considered the largest single halophytic mangrove unit in the world (Bhowmik & Cabral 2013).

Prain (1903) recorded a total of 334 plant species, which differs greatly from other non-deltaic mangroves and upland forests. It is a tropical moist forest having a mosaic pattern of old growth and successional vegetation (Uddin *et al.* 2022; Rahman 2020). Sundari (*Heritiera fomes*) and Gewa (*Excoecaria agallocha*) are the dominant species in the old-growth forests with uneven distributions of Dhundul (*Xylocarpus granatum*) and Kakra (*Bruguiera sp*) (Rahman *et al.* 2015; Siddiqui & Rahman 2019). Golpata (*Nypa fruticans*) and Hantol (*Phoenix paludosa*) are also indicator plant species of the mangrove (Rahman 2023a). Sometimes successional forests are dominated by Keora (*Sonneratia apetala*), aquatic plants and dune vegetation. There are strong

correlations among vegetations, salinity, freshwater flushing, silting, inundation and mudflat accretion (Rahman 2023 g, h, i, f).

The mangrove is the habitat of many species of birds, mammals, reptiles, amphibians, fishes, shrimps and other invertebrates (Rahman 2015; Sinha & Prasad 2020; Ramakrishna & Sethy 2006). Hog deer, water buffalo, swamp deer, Javan rhinoceros, single-horned rhinoceros and the mugger crocodile became extinct at the beginning of the last century (Rahman 2000). It is the paradise of the eponymous Royal Bengal tiger, saltwater crocodile and spotted deer. Besides, dolphins, rhesus monkeys, snakes, river terrapin, forest owls, sea eagles, Indian flap-shelled turtles, peacock soft-shelled turtles, swamp partridge, trogon, ground thrush, yellow monitor, water monitor, Indian python, fishing cats, macaques, forest wagtail, wild boar, green frog, grey mongoose, scarlet minivet, fox, ring lizard, jungle cat, flying fox, pangolin, pigmy woodpecker, brown wing kingfisher, racket-tailed drongo, chital and other threatened species live in the Sundarbans. Climate change has a significant impact on the wildlife of this mangrove (Mahadevia & Vikas 2012; Mukul *et al.* 2019; Agrawala *et al.* 2003; Dasgupta *et al.* 2016). Therefore, the study aims to assess the types of climatic stressors and their impacts on the flora and fauna of the Sundarbans mangrove of Bangladesh.

Methodology

Both primary and secondary data were used for this study. The secondary data were critically reviewed to frame a conceptual framework. Local people were personally interviewed to identify the flora and fauna. Three focus group discussions were carried out incorporating the respondents from diverse stakeholders to assess the impact of sea level rise, storminess and salinity. A total of ten key informants were interviewed to find out the solutions. Content analysis was done to interpret the data.

Sea level rise

The respondents predicted that a one-metre rise in sea level will destroy the whole ecosystem of Sundarbans mangrove and littoral forests of Bangladesh. Dune vegetation will be submerged underwater. The pioneer or indicator species Sundari (*Heritiera fomes*) will be replaced by Keora (*Sonneratia apetala*) and Bain (*Avicennia Officinalis*). The ground animal will lose their habitats. Herbivorous animals like deer, monkeys and wild boar will face a shortage of food. Carnivorous

animals like tigers and fishing cats will face the same problem due to the lack of herbivorous animals in the forest. Marine turtles, crabs, shrimps, crocodiles, frogs, snakes, freshwater fishes and dolphins will lose their breeding grounds and habitat as well.

Low-level rise

Mammals and reptiles in the forests will be highly vulnerable. The same animals residing on the islands will be threatened.

Medium level rise

A good number of wildlife species living in the forests notably mammals and reptiles will be vulnerable. The same group living on islands will face a high risk of extinction

High-level rise

The whole dune vegetation will be submerged underwater. The pioneer of indicator plant species will be replaced by the stress-tolerant or invasive very quickly. All ground animals will lose their habitats. Herbivorous animals will face a shortage of food, and carnivores will face the same problem due to the lack of herbivores.

Storminess

The respondents noted that the recent tropical cyclones impacted Sundarbans through three primary mechanisms: wind damage, storm surge, and sedimentation. Many affected areas have become unsuitable for habitation. Most of the inhabitants will be climate refugees with the repetition of such cyclones. Strong winds uproot, topple stems, break off trunks and defoliate the canopy. Taller stems are uprooted and knocked over when a storm ashore comes. Sediments carried by storm surges are deposited on the forest floor as the surge recedes, causing plant mortality by interfering with root and soil gas exchange, leading to the eventual death of the plants. Storm surges reduce the viability of seeds, seedling germination and seedling recruitment. The recovery of forest dynamics from cyclone damage can be altered by other kinds of changes to the landscape. Many exotic plant species can rapidly colonize disturbed areas. Dunes and beaches are washed away.

The respondents added that the cyclones do not affect the Royal Bengal tigers too much as they can swim a long distance. But the problem is that they may lose bearing. When they do not know in which direction they have to move, they may die due to exhaustion. Strong wind destroys honey bee colonies causing high mortality. Woodpeckers, sea turtles and parrots are vulnerable to cyclones. The arboreal monkey and lizards face a shortage of food. Fish dies when the decay of foliage stripped from trees lower oxygen levels in the water. Ground birds are severely affected by losing their habitats, nesting and breeding sites.

Salinity

The respondents pointed out that the Sundari, the pioneer tree species suffer from the 'Top dyeing' disease with the increase of salinity. Salinity increases the tree mortality rate by reducing the production of new leaves, leaf longevity and the leaf area. The net photosynthesis rate, stomata conductance and transpiration rate of leaves decrease with the increase of salt. The respondents also believe that Royal Bengal Tigers are suffering from various diseases by drinking saline water and their normal behaviour is also being changed. Aquatic organisms will migrate inward. Many fish species and other crustaceans utilize fresh water for spawning and juvenile feeding. The Hilsa needs less salinity to lay their eggs and enter various creeks in search of sweet water. The hatchlings move towards the sea where they attain adulthood, before returning to the rivers. The migration of fish species will harm the economy of the country.

How to combat it?

- * Designing and establishing a sea-level / climate modelling network
- * Establishing databases and information systems
- * Data collection of Sundarbans' resources and their uses
- * Integrated coastal and marine management
- * Monitoring the impact of climate change on the Royal Bengal Tiger, crocodiles and Sundari tree
- * Coastal vulnerability and risk assessment
- * Economic valuation of Sundarbans' resources

- * Improving catchment management
- * Facilitating natural regeneration and natural succession of native tree species
- * Increasing waterfront setbacks in beachfront areas
- * Education on climate change and emergency preparedness needs to take place at all levels by incorporating it into education curricula
- * Creating public awareness through mass media
- * Developing coastal infrastructure
- * Initiating community-based coastal forestation
- * Protecting existing mangroves against encroachment and cutting
- * Afforestation and reforestation by salt-tolerant species
- * Initiating ex-situ conservation of rare species
- * Establishing mechanisms to promote carbon uptake
- * Raising funds for the conservation programme
- * Strict control of Tigers' poaching

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